

CARBON FIBER EPOXY ATHERMAL STRUCTURES FOR OPTICAL FIBER GRATING WAVELENGTH STABILIZATION

C S Shin¹, Yen-Chang Huang² and Shien-Kuei Liaw³

¹Mechanical Engineering, National Taiwan University,
No.1, Sec.4, Roosevelt Road, Taipei, 10617, Taiwan, (R.O.C.)
Email: csshin@ntu.edu.tw, web page: <http://www.me.ntu.edu.tw>

² Mechanical Engineering, National Taiwan University,
No.1, Sec.4, Roosevelt Road, Taipei, 10617, Taiwan, (R.O.C.)
Email: second.r01522513@ntu.edu.tw, web page: <http://www.me.ntu.edu.tw/>

³ 2Elelctronic and computer engineering, National Taiwan Univ of Science andTechnology, Taipei, Taiwan, No.43, Sec. 4, Keelung Rd., Da'an Dist., Taipei 106, Taiwan (R.O.C.)
Email: skliaw@mail.ntust.edu.tw, web page: <http://www.ntust.edu.tw>

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ABSTRACT

Fiber Bragg gratings (FBG) are commonly employed as wavelength reference or wavelength-selective component in fiber sensor interrogation and telecommunications systems. Thermally induced shift in FBG wavelength may seriously compromise the precision and performance of these systems. A number of athermal structures have been proposed to keep FBG wavelength as temperature insensitive as possible and their performance varied and the best compensation reported was to reduced the FBG wavelength drift from ~ 10 pm/ $^{\circ}$ C to around 1 pm/ $^{\circ}$ C. Much higher compensation may be needed in other fiber gratings and systems.

The current work proposes to use carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites for this job. The thermal expansion coefficients of carbon fibers is negative along its longitudinal axis while that of epoxy resins is positive. By simply stacking laminae with different fiber directions, it is possible to produce a laminate that will create a designated amount of thermal strain to nullify the drift in FBG wavelength. A nominally flat $0^{\circ}/51^{\circ}$ laminate is found able to reduce the thermal wavelength drift to ~ 0.6 pm/ $^{\circ}$ C. More compensation is possible if the laminate has an initial curvature and better still if the curved laminate has both ends fixed to a third restrainer material. Systematic numerical analysis showed that compensation up to ~ 70 pm/ $^{\circ}$ C is possible with these simple structures. Since the width and thickness of the restrainer will affect the resulting degree of compensation, this may be used to advantage to fine tune the compensation in-situ. Some of these designs were fabricated and satisfactory wavelength stability was successfully demonstrated on a standalone fiber Bragg grating. Apart from having a much wider range of compensation, the current composite structures are much lighter, smaller, cheaper and easier to mass fabricate than conventional ones.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to its all-fiber configuration, great flexibility and highly efficient filtering functions, fiber Bragg grating (FBG) technology has been widely used in telecommunications systems and in wavelength measuring systems for fiber sensors. Such systems must be designed to fulfill very stringent performance requirements which call for a good precision and stability in the Bragg wavelength of the FBG. The thermal drift of the Bragg wavelength of FBG is unacceptably high when the FBG and will seriously compromise the precision and performance of wavelength reference or wavelength-selective component. Accurate wavelength referencing requires either temperature

calibration, stringent temperature control or temperature compensation of the wavelength reference devices. A number of passive and active mechanisms [1-6] have been proposed to keep FBG wavelength as temperature insensitive as possible. Passive athermal structure is preferred as it has no power consumption and is more likely to remain maintenance-free for long-term applications. The underlying principle of the passive structures is to create a thermal strain that has exactly the opposite effect on wavelength as the temperature induced change. The thermal strain is obtained by employing dissimilar materials with carefully designed dimensions, shapes and arrangement. The performance of these structures varied and the best compensation reported was to reduce the FBG wavelength drift from ~ 10 pm/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to around 1 pm/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Long period fiber gratings have thermal wavelength shift many times that of FBG and calls for large compensation to remain thermally stable. Over-compensation in FBG may sometimes be needed in some optical systems in order to cover for the thermal shift caused by components other than the fiber grating. Most of these athermal structures suffered the drawbacks of being bulky and required precision machining to produce the complicated designs. Moreover, although the degree of compensation can be designed beforehand, further adjustment is normally not possible once the structure is fabricated.

The current work proposes to use carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composites for this job. The thermal expansion coefficients of carbon fibers is negative along its longitudinal axis while that of epoxy resins is positive. By suitably stacking laminae with different fiber directions, it is possible to produce a laminate that will generate a designated amount of thermal strain to nullify the drift in FBG wavelength. A schematic illustration of a $[0^{\circ}/\theta]$ laminate is shown in Fig.1. The laminate is flat just after curing. On cooling down to room temperature, differential thermal expansion will cause the laminate to bend into certain initial curvature. An FBG is then stuck on its top surface. When temperature rises, the amount of differential thermal expansion will decrease and the initial curvature will tends to resolve, creating a negative strain that may counteract the thermal drift in the FBG wavelength.

Figure 1: Schematic illustration of the principle of the composite athermal device.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Graphite fiber reinforced Epoxy laminates were fabricated using T300/E3501 unidirectional pre-impregnated tape. The graphite fiber has a negative thermal expansion while the epoxy resin has a positive one. This gives a coefficient of thermal expansion of $-1.8 \times 10^{-8}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ along the 0° orientation (i.e. fiber direction) and $3 \times 10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ along the 90° orientation. Finite element analysis (FEA) using the

package ABAQUS has been carried out on a series of different lamina orientations and stacking sequences to short-list the suitable laminates. Fig.2 shows some typical FEA models. Besides the nominal flat laminate (Fig.2a), laminates with different curvature mounted on a restrainer plate have also been analyzed. Based on the analysis, 2-layer laminate with the stacking sequence of $[0^\circ/37^\circ]$, $[0^\circ/45^\circ]$, $[0^\circ/51^\circ]$, $[0^\circ/52^\circ]$, $[0^\circ/53^\circ]$, $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ have been fabricated. Optical fibers with Bragg grating were then stuck on the convex side of the composite strip along the 0° direction using a cyanoacrylate based adhesive (Loctite 401). The devices were then tested in an environmental chamber that can control temperature to within $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 2: typical finite element model of FBG sticking on a composite structure (a) a nominally flat laminate; (b) a curved laminate mounted on a restrainer plate.

Fiber Bragg gratings (FBG) were fabricated by side writing using a phase mask of period of $1.05\mu\text{m}$. The reflectivity of the FBG was about 99%, and the peak wavelength was between 1540nm to 1550nm. The reflected Bragg wavelength was monitored with an Anritsu MS9710C optical Spectrum Analyzer (OSA), which has an accuracy of 20 pm and a short term drift of ± 5 pm.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Nominally flat laminates

Fig. 3a shows the predicted compensating capability of a 2-layer laminate with stacking sequences from $[0^\circ/34^\circ]$ to $[0^\circ/39^\circ]$, it can be seen that a stacking sequence between $[0^\circ/36^\circ]$ and $[0^\circ/37^\circ]$ will be able to completely nullify the thermal drift in FBG wavelength. On fabricating and actually testing the $[0^\circ/37^\circ]$ laminate, an average of drift of $2.3\text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$ was observed instead of the near $0\text{ pm}/^\circ\text{C}$ expected (Fig. 3b).

Fig.3 (a) finite element predicted compensation capability of a series of 2-layer laminates; (b) actual performance of the $[0^\circ/37^\circ]$ laminate.

There are a number of reasons that may lead to this discrepancy: firstly, the material data such as elastic moduli and thermal expansion coefficients of the composite, adhesive and optical fiber are values collected from the literature and may not reflect the accurate values of our materials. Secondly, the measured thickness of the adhesive is liable to error as pressing with different forces with the vernier caliper gave slightly different readings. Anyway the finite element results shows that more compensation will result with a larger difference in fiber orientations. Since it is still under-compensation with the 37° orientation, we need to increase the angle of the second layer.

Table 1 shows the resulting thermal drift in Bragg wavelength of the FBG obtained when stacking sequences with the second layer fiber orientation larger than 37° were tested. A stacking sequence of $[0^\circ/51^\circ]$ seems to give an acceptable result.

Stacking sequence	$[0^\circ/37^\circ]$	$[0^\circ/45^\circ]$	$[0^\circ/51^\circ]$	$[0^\circ/52^\circ]$	$[0^\circ/53^\circ]$	$[0^\circ/90^\circ]$
Resulting thermal wavelength drift ($\text{pm}/^\circ\text{C}$)	2.3	1.84	0.66	-3.04	-5.51	-7.3

Table 1: Measured thermal drift in Bragg wavelength for different laminate stacking sequences.

It can be noted from both the finite element results in Fig.3A and the observed results in table 1 that the compensation capability of the composite laminate is very sensitive to the angular orientations of the fiber. A one degree difference in fiber orientation can change the compensation capability by more than $1\text{pm}/^\circ\text{C}$. This is undesirable because aligning the angle of the lamina is liable to error and an error of one degree is not uncommon. During manual stacking, with the help of some simple fixtures, the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ can reliably be positioned to accurate orientation. For intermediate angles such as $[0^\circ/51^\circ]$, the angular accuracy will be lower. However, the nominally flat $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ laminate gives too much over-compensation for ordinary FBG application. This represents the maximum compensation obtainable from the current layout and finite element analysis suggested that increasing the laminate to more layer will not give higher compensation.

3.2 Curved laminate mounted on a restrainer plate

From the above, we conclude that: (1) the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ cross ply configuration is preferred to enable easy and accurate angular alignment; (2) other means instead of manipulating the fiber orientation to adjust for compensation capability is preferable. To these ends, a curved laminate with the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ or $[90^\circ/0^\circ]$ stacking sequence is employed. The curved laminate is mounted on a restrainer plate as shown in Fig.4a. Variation in compensation capability is achieved through changing the dimensional parameters H, L, W, B and the restrainer material. Fig.4b shows a series of curved laminates with different combinations of H, L and W. H and L are controlled by suitable curing moulds.

Figure 4 (a) schematics of the curved laminate device; (b) a series of fabricated curved composite laminates with different combinations of H, L and W.

Fig.5 shows typical finite element results on some particular combination of dimensional parameters and stacking sequences. A 3 mm thick ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UPE) is used as the restrainer plate material. For a $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ (0° is along the longitudinal direction and the 0° lamina is the top layer) laminate with $H=7\text{mm}$ and $L=25\text{mm}$, the amount of compensated drift in the FBG wavelength is from +4 to $-8\text{ pm}^\circ\text{C}$ for a range of W/B ratios (Fig.5a). If a large over-compensation is needed, the $[90^\circ/0^\circ]$ (0° is along the longitudinal direction and the 90° lamina is the top layer) laminate with $H=3\text{mm}$ and $L=25\text{mm}$ can be used. Over-compensation to about $-66\text{ pm}^\circ\text{C}$ can be achieved (Fig.5b).

Figure 5 Compensated thermal wavelength shift for various W/B ratios for laminates stacking sequences of (a) $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$, $H=7\text{mm}$, $L=25\text{mm}$; (b) $[90^\circ/0^\circ]$, $H=3\text{mm}$, $L=25\text{mm}$.

Fig. 6a shows a more refined calculation for the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$, $H=7\text{mm}$ and $L=25\text{mm}$ with W of 25, 28 and 30mm for different B. The predicted amount of compensated wavelength drift for each geometry is given beside the corresponding symbol. Fig. 6b shows the wavelength measurement results at different temperature for the particular dimension of $B=50\text{mm}$ and $W=28\text{mm}$. The predicted thermal wavelength shift is shown as a dotted line. The measured shift is close to the predicted line, but the shifts for heating up and cooling down are slightly different. The reason for this difference may be attributed to the transient condition in the environmental chamber. Temperature was set to change by $0.7\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and was read with a thermal resistor sensor placed close to the structure. However, the air temperature may not be the same as the device temperature. Moreover, there was probably a temperature distribution over different parts of the device and that distribution is likely to be different during heating and cooling. All in all, the average wavelength shift during heating is $-1.055\text{ pm}^\circ\text{C}$ and that for cooling is $-1.032\text{ pm}^\circ\text{C}$. These compare favourably with the calculated $-1.254\text{ pm}^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 6 (a) a more refined calculation of wavelength shift and (b) comparison between predicted and measured wavelength shift.

Besides being easier to get aligned with the 0° and 90° stacking, the overall geometry of the current design can be accurately controlled fairly easily. Reproducible H and L can be achieved by using suitable curing moulds. The width B and W can be controlled by precision machining. Moreover, from Fig.6a, it can be seen that by reducing the width B of the restrainer plate, the compensation will decrease. This implies that one can cut or file away materials from the restrainer plate to adjust the compensation to the desired value even its initial performance is not exactly satisfactory. The latter is another strong point of the current design which is not available in previously published athermal packaging structures.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Carbon fiber composite laminate with suitable stacking orientation has been shown to be able to provide compensation for the thermal drift of the Bragg wavelength of fiber gratings. The compensation capability of a nominally flat 2-layer laminate can be controlled by modifying the fiber orientation and can achieve a maximum compensated drift of $-7.3\text{pm}/^\circ\text{C}$ in the cross-ply $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ configuration. A curved 2-layer cross-ply laminate mounted on restrainer plate can achieve nearly ten times that amount of compensation. Moreover, since the degree of compensation depends on the geometry and dimensions, it is possible to fine tune the compensation by removing material from the restrainer plate.

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